

BREAKING THE CHAINS OF HOMOPHOBIA: A CALL TO ACTION FOR LGBTQ+ EQUALITY

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Abstract

This paper addresses the detrimental impact of supporting homophobic Christian organisations on the LGBTQ+ community and urges recipients to reconsider their donations. It highlights the link between such donations and the perpetuation of harmful legislation targeting queer individuals, leading to increased societal stigma, mental health issues, and higher suicide rates among LGBTQ+ youth. The letter challenges misconceptions about religion and homosexuality, emphasising the moral imperative to support inclusive charities. It calls for action to protect the rights and well-being of LGBTQ+ individuals, with stress on the importance of social acceptance and equality.

Keywords: LGBTQ+, homophobia, legislation, discrimination, religion, inclusion, gender, equity, stigma, teens, youths.